

Guava fruits storage shelf life determination using Electronic Nose

Ashok Kanade¹ and Arvind Shaligram²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Electronic Science, P.V.P. College,
Pravaranagar - 413713,

²Professor and Head, Department of Electronic-Science,
Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune - 411007

Abstract:

The e-nose system is developed in the present research work and extensively used for determination of storage shelf life of guava fruit since harvest in two different storage treatments. Two storage treatments were conducted; one is with paper wrapping and another in plastic folded bag. PCA, MLP Feed forward neural network based PARC techniques were used to distinguish the guava fruits with different storage treatment and storage time. Result shows the ability of the developed system to distinguish storage shelf life of guava fruit stored in different storage conditions.

Keywords : E-nose, Guava fruit ripening, Principle component analysis, gas sensor, storage self-life of guava determination.

1. Introduction:

In recent years, there has been a considerable increase in demand for better quality fruit due to globalization of market. Consequently, it is important to evaluate fruit maturation stage and storage shelf-life. Many methods of monitoring maturation and shelf-life have already been proposed. The main disadvantages of these methods are that they are not practical for cultivars or storage stations, and most of them require the destruction of the samples used for analysis. This may be the reason that optimal harvest date and predictions of shelf-life are mainly based on practical experience.

1) Leaving these critical decisions to subjective interpretation implies that large quantities of fruit are always harvested too soon or too late and reach consumer markets in poor condition. A strategy for evaluating the maturation and shelf-life consists of sensing the aromatic volatiles emitted from fruit by using electronic nose systems. 2) Metabolic changes are mostly due to the following four items: post-harvest ripening, respiration, fermentation and phenolic oxidation. 3) Aroma is an important food quality attribute. The aroma of a food product is detected when its volatiles enter the nasal passages at the back of the throat and is perceived by receptors of the olfactory system. 4) Concerning the exploitation of the information contained in the heads pace of fruit, they have been studied in the recent past with the conventional analytical chemistry equipment, and the correlation between the state of over-ripening and the fruit aroma has also been found both in quantitative and in qualitative terms. Besides, some specific compounds

have been identified to be responsible of the aroma of particular fruit. In the last decade, the electronic nose offers a fast and nondestructive alternative to sense aroma, and, hence, may be advantageously used to predict the optimal harvest date. Some authors reported positive applications of electronic nose technology to the discrimination of fruit of different qualities, with oranges. 5) Tomatoes. 6) Apples. 7) and cherry. 8) but as yet few literatures refer to control the fruit maturity in the shelf-life state. The objective of this study was (1) To evaluate the capacity of developed electronic nose in monitoring the change in volatile production of Guava fruit during different storage treatments and storage time (2) To study Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and radar plot to obtain whether the electronic nose is able to distinguish guavas indifferent storage condition and storage time (3) to design the pattern recognition module using MLP NN for prediction of storage shelf life of guava.

2. Method and Material:

2.1 Electronic Nose System :

The static system is the basic one, used to measure the sensors steady-state response. Figure 1 shows block diagram of designed odor delivery system for fruit odor sensing. This system consists of small centrifugal air pump, concentration chamber, measurement chamber, metal oxide gas sensor array, signal conditioning circuit, DAQ card connected to laptop containing GUI software, vacuum pump, electronic valves, gas pipes, driving circuit etc.

Figure 1 Schematic of developed E-nose system measurements and gas flow during experiment

All the gas connections are made up of inert TPL Polyurethane 8mm x 6 mm tubing and fittings. The sensor array is situated in measurement chamber. The fruit samples are placed into concentration chamber for accumulation of odor. This accumulated odor is introduced into the measurement chamber for measurement through push-fit type solenoid valves and gas vials for constant time duration. The centrifugal air pump was mounted outside the concentration chamber used for pushing the sample headspace from the concentration chamber to the measurement chamber. After exposure of odor, the sensor array was given sufficient time to reach its steady state. The sensors response was recorded into computer via DAQ card connected to USB port of the computer with specially developed software. The electronic solenoid valves V1, V2 and V3 are used to guide the fresh air and headspace as per requirement in ODS. The odor flow is controlled through a rotameter. The vacuum pump was used to clean the measurement chamber with fresh air. The design and operation of developed electronic nose system explained in our research article [9].

2.2 Experimental Material:

For storage shelf life determination, 30 mature green guava fruits (about to ripe) were used and two storage treatments were conducted. For prediction study, 20 fruits of same variety were selected and harvested from orchard near 1km from the previous place of orchard and two storage treatments were conducted. The harvested fruits were selected, washed under clean running water and immersed in a 1% sodium hypochlorite solution at 25°C for 5 minutes for disinfection. Two storage treatments were conducted in laboratory conditions. One batch of 15 guava fruits storage conducted in laboratory condition with paper wrapping and placed in cartoon box. The second batch of 15 fruits placed in plastic folded bag storage. The

fruits were stored in a shelf of the laboratory for 8 days at temperature and relative humidity maintained at 26 ± 1 °C and $41 \pm 5\%$ respectively. The samples for prediction study also treated with above method.

2.3 Experimental Design:

The experimental design was completely randomized with each fruit treated as an experimental unit. Each fruit Guava fruit samples removed from storage at days 0, 2, 4, 6 and 8 (day 2 is the second day since harvest, day 0 is the picked day) and evaluated using electronic nose with 2 sets of observations for to each fruit sample. Each observation set consisted of 10 repetitions. For cross validation, the same treatments were applied for all guava fruits from the other orchard for 8 day storage.

2.4 Data Base Generation:

Data sets were gathered chronologically and stored in a file represented by Sij, where i indicate storage type and j indicates day number. The whole exercise of recording data sets was carried out for eight days, resulting in the database generation scheme is tabulated in Table 1

Table 1 Database structure of storage shelf life of guava fruits

Storage type	Day0	Day2	Day4	Day6	Day8
Paper wrapping	S10	S12	S14	S16	S18
Plastic folded bag	S20	S22	S24	S26	S28

The quality of database generated through experiment was tested using PCA analysis. The ANN was designed and optimized for prediction of storage shelf-life of guava fruit in five groups as day 0, day2, day4, day6 and day8. In this experiment, the MLP back propagation ANN trained with the Levenberg-Marquard training algorithm. The training used all the 8 sensors as inputs, 10 neurons in the single hidden layer and three neurons at output layer. The activation functions used are sigmoid and identity functions at the hidden and output layer, respectively.

3. Result and Discussion:

3.1 Classification using PCA :

Fig. 2 shows PCA analysis plot for guava fruits stored using paper wrapping and represent the variation during day 0 to day 8 storage times.

Figure 2. 1 PCA of Guava fruit stored in paper wrapping

The processed data showed erratic shift of the clusters and no particular trend with storage time. The first principal component, PC1, explains 87.9% of the total variation, while 12.1% of the total variance is explained by PC2. The five clusters are clearly separated, thus the system has enough resolution to explain the different storage shelf-life period of guava fruit.

Fig. 3 shows PCA analysis plot of data obtained from guava fruits stored in plastic folded bag. The two principal components {PC_{1,n}, PC_{2,n}} was obtained and has the two greatest variances: 99.8% and 0.2% respectively. The scores of the five groups of fruits are plotted for principal component 2 (PC2) versus principal component 1 (PC1). The processed data shows a shift erratic of the groups at different storage time along the first principal component, and no particular trend with the guava fruit storage time along the axis-y. Thus the developed system has ability to trace the storage shelf-life period and type of storage treatment adequately.

Figure 3 PCA of Guava fruit stored in plastic folded bag

From both PCA plots it is observed that the discrimination is little in initial storage days; but after

2nd day in paper wrapping storage and from 4th day in plastic folded bag it increased significantly.

3.2 Prediction of storage shelf life using MLP NN

The dataset collected over eight days span of guava fruits using e-nose in two storage treatments were analyzed using MLP feed forward neural network with back propagation training algorithm. The average prediction results obtained using feed forward ANN with % accuracy are shown in below table 2 and 3 for two storage treatments.

Table 2 Performance of trained pattern recognition modules in paper wrapping storage

Fruits Class	Samples		Prediction performance	% performance
	Train	Test		
Day0	45	30	23/30	76.7
Day2	45	30	24/30	80
Day4	45	30	28/30	93.3
Day6	45	30	27/30	90
Day8	45	30	29/30	96.66
Average Performance			26.2/30	87.33

The average prediction results obtained by MLP NN for paper wrapped storage treatment are 87.33 %. The average prediction results of plastic folded bag storage treatment are 85.33% and 77.9 % for ANN and fuzzy logic pattern recognition methods respectively.

Table 3 Performance of trained pattern recognition modules in plastic folded bag storage

Fruits Class	Samples		Prediction performance	% performance
	Train	Test		
Day0	45	30	24/30	80
Day2	45	30	23/30	76.6
Day4	45	30	25/30	83.3
Day6	45	30	27/30	90
Day8	45	30	29/30	96.6
Average Performance			25.6/30	85.33

4 Conclusion :

The obtained results proved that guava fruits with different storage time can be monitored by the developed system, but very clear separation among all groups of different storage time was not achieved. By

PCA it is clearly seen that the system could more clearly discrimination storage time of Guava fruits in paper wrapped storage than one in plastic folded bag. The result suggest that the developed system could be used as alternative way for determining storage shelf life of guava using conventional physico-chemical methods.

The average efficiency achieved using developed classifier systems is about 90%, if human grading taken as reference level is assumed to be 100% accurate. However, 10% variation is also due to individual judgment of human-graders in perceiving the ripening level of fruit during manual grading, which of course is inevitable. The repeatability of the developed system is found to be 100% from rigorous experimental work.

5 References :

- 1) L. R. Verma and V. K. Joshi, "Postharvest Technology of Fruits and Vegetables: General concepts and principles", vol. 1. Indus Publishing, 2000.
- 2) M. Benady et al., "Fruit ripeness determination by electronic sensing of aromatic volatiles," *Trans. ASAE*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 251–257, 1995.
- 3) H. Young et al., "Causal effects of aroma compounds on Royal Gala apple flavours," *J. Sci. Food Agric.*, vol. 71, no. 3, pp. 329–336, 1996.
- 4) S. Oshita et al., "Discrimination of odors emanating from 'La France' pear by semi-conducting polymer sensors," *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 209–216, 2000.
- 5) A. H. Gómez, J. Wang, G. Hu, and A. G. Pereira, "Electronic nose technique potential monitoring mandarin maturity," *Sensors Actuators B Chem.*, vol. 113, no. 1, pp. 347–353, 2006.
- 6) A. Z. Berna, J. Lammertyn, S. Saevels, C. Di Natale, and B. M. Nicolai, "Electronic nose systems to study shelf life and cultivar effect on tomato aroma profile," *Sensors Actuators B Chem.*, vol. 97, no. 2, pp. 324–333, 2004.
- 7) A. Z. Berna, J. Lammertyn, S. Saevels, C. Di Natale, and B. M. Nicolai, "Electronic nose systems to study shelf life and cultivar effect on tomato aroma profile," *Sensors Actuators B Chem.*, vol. 97, no. 2, pp. 324–333, 2004.
- 8) A. Z. Berna, J. Lammertyn, S. Saevels, C. Di Natale, and B. M. Nicolai, "Electronic nose systems to study shelf life and cultivar effect on tomato aroma profile," *Sensors Actuators B Chem.*, vol. 97, no. 2, pp. 324–333, 2004.
- 9) A. Kanade et al., "Development of an e-Nose using metal oxide semiconductor sensors for the classification of climacteric fruits", *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Vol. 5, no. 2, pp.467-471, 2014.
